

1 **The Holocene**

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3 **Modeling the retreat of the Aneto Glacier (Spanish Pyrenees) since the**
4 **Little Ice Age, and its accelerated shrinkage over recent decades**

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21

22 **Abstract**

23 The Aneto, located on the Maladeta Massif (Central Pyrenees), is the largest
24 glacier of the Pyrenees. The glacier is 675 m long, occupies an area of 48.64
25 ha and has a maximum altitude of 3269 m. In this study, we present a detailed
26 area, volume, ice thickness, and Equilibrium Line Altitude reconstruction of
27 the glacier for different periods (LIA, 1957, 1983, 2000, 2006, 2015, and
28 2017) and analyze its retreat. To estimate the glacier extent during the LIA,
29 the moraines were mapped by using photo interpretation techniques whereas
30 for the recent stages digital satellite images and aerial photographs were
31 used. Moreover, we estimated the topography of the glacier using a simple
32 steady-state model that assumes a perfectly plastic ice rheology, which
33 allowed reconstructing the theoretical ice profiles of the glacier. To

34 reconstruct the ice surface, a digital elevation model was created and
35 combined with the bedrock topography in order to obtain the ice thickness
36 of each stage. The results of the study reveal a considerable retreat of the
37 Aneto Glacier since the LIA. The length of the glacier has reduced from 1970
38 to 675 m from LIA to 2017, and its tongue has retreated from 2385 to 3029
39 m a.s.l. Furthermore, the glaciated area has been reduced from 245 to 48.64
40 ha from LIA to 2017 and the ELA has risen from 2919 to 3139 m a.s.l. The
41 data obtained indicates that in the LIA–2017 period the glacier volume has
42 been reduced from $82.57 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ to $3.48 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ and the maximum
43 ice thickness from 95 to 27m. We also reconstructed the climatic conditions,
44 showing an increase in temperature of $\sim 1.14^\circ\text{C}$ from LIA to 2017. These data
45 reveal a vast retreat of the glacier since the LIA, which has accelerated since
46 the 1980's and even more since the year 2000.

47 Keywords

48 Aneto, Equilibrium Line Altitude, glacier retreat, glacier volume, ice
49 thickness, Little Ice Age, numerical modeling, Pyrenees Received 3
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52 Introduction

53 Glaciers are key indicators of climate change due to their high sensitivity to
54 precipitation and air temperature fluctuations (Bauder et al., 2007; Fischer et
55 al., 2015; Houghton et al., 2001; Mackintosh et al., 2017; Oerlemans, 2005;
56 Sutherland, 1984; among others). Thus, knowledge of the ice thickness
57 distribution of the world's glaciers is a fundamental prerequisite for a wide
58 range of studies, such as water resource management and the study of the
59 impacts of climate change (Langhammer et al., 2019). Also, knowing the
60 thickness of glacier ice is critical for predicting the rate and timing of glacier
61 retreat and disappearance, and the associated environmental and social
62 impacts (Farinotti et al., 2019; Welty et al., 2020). Projections of future
63 glacier change, estimates of the available freshwater resources or
64 assessments of potential sea-level rise require glacier ice thickness
65 estimations to be accurately constrained (Farinotti et al., 2019). Furthermore,
66 the Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA) is a useful indicator to analyze the
67 relationship between glaciers and climate (Nesje, 2013). The ELA is a
68 climate-sensitive parameter and it is theoretically defined as the location on

69 a glacier where annual accumulation is balanced by annual ablation, that is,
70 net surface mass balance equals zero (Braithwaite, 2015; Carr et al., 2010;
71 Cogley et al., 2011; González-Reyes et al., 2019; Lie et al., 2003; Rupper
72 and Roe, 2008).

73 The Little Ice Age (LIA) constitutes one of the coldest stages of the Holocene
74 that favored the expansion of glaciers in most of the highest mountain ranges
75 on Earth (Bradley and Jones, 1992; Serrano et al., 2018). The LIA is the last
76 “stage” of the Neoglacial period. The Neoglacial period took place from the
77 end of the Holocene Thermal Maximum, dated between ~11 and ~5 ka (Gar-
78 cía-Ruiz et al., 2020; Renssen et al., 2012), until the end of the LIA. The
79 timing of the LIA is still under discussion. According to Porter (1986), the
80 LIA period took place between AD 1250 and 1850–1860, while Le Roy
81 Ladurie (1967) and Fagan (2000) dated the beginning of the LIA at around
82 AD 1300 and the end around AD 1850–1860. Other authors indicated that
83 the extreme phase of the LIA encompass between 1550 and 1850 (Jones and
84 Bradley, 1992) and the main phase between 1550 and 1700 (Lamb, 1977).
85 Since this period, after the mid-19th century, glaciers began to retreat, in both
86 the Northern and Southern hemispheres (Oerlemans, 2005; Wanner et al.,
87 2008). This decrease has not been continuous, with periods of glacial
88 advance, stabilization, and retreat, as also recorded in several mid-latitude
89 environments such as the Alps (Zemp et al., 2015). However, in the last
90 decades, the rate of shrinkage of glaciers is increasing.

91 In the Pyrenees, the LIA has been constrained between the 14th and 19th
92 centuries (Grove, 2004). The end of the LIA in the Pyrenees can be set
93 around 1850, according to the data reported by Büntgen et al. (2017), who
94 based on tree-ring evidences reconstructed warmer conditions after 1850.
95 René (2013) estimated that there were 52 glaciers in the Pyrenees in 1850.
96 After 1850–1860, the Pyrenean glaciers started a slow retreat that became
97 progressively more rapid during the 20th century. By 1984, there were 39
98 glaciers (Arenillas-Parra et al., 2008) and by 2016 the number decreased to
99 only 19 (Rico et al., 2017). Many of the Pyrenean glaciers have disappeared
100 during the last four decades, and the extent of the remaining glaciers has been
101 greatly reduced (Chueca et al., 2002; García-Ruiz et al., 2014). Recent
102 estimations point out that they occupied an area of 321 ha in 2008, which has
103 reduced to 242ha in 2016 (Oliva et al., 2019; Rico et al., 2017). According
104 to López-Moreno et al. (2006), the rate of shrinkage depends on the local

105 topographical setting and micro- climatic conditions, being the glacial
106 features of the highest areas of the Pyrenees frequently classified as small
107 cirque glaciers (Chueca et al., 1998; Chueca and Julián, 2004a; Martí-Bono
108 and García-Ruiz, 1994) due to its topographical settings.

109 The gradual warming trend initiated during the second half of the 19th
110 century promoted the progressive shrinking of the glaciers in the Pyrenees,
111 where the total glaciated area during the LIA was reduced by 80% during the
112 first half of the 20th century (Serrano et al., 2018). To determine a proper
113 diagnosis of the state of a glacier, it is necessary an accurate estimate of the
114 remaining ice volume, and the quantification of ice motion. Additionally,
115 providing evidence of past and recent changes in ice volume allows for
116 understanding the evolution of the glacier in past and present periods of
117 climate change (López-Moreno et al., 2018). Moreover, projections of the
118 impact of the glaciers mass loss require an estimate of the ice volume stored
119 within present-day glaciers, and for regional to local-scale projections, the
120 ice thick- ness distribution can also be essential (Farinotti et al., 2019; Gabbi
121 et al., 2012; Huss and Hock, 2015). Understanding the evolution and spatial
122 variability of glaciers may contribute to a better knowledge of the impact,
123 trends, and rates of ongoing climate change (Bauder et al., 2007).

124 According to Marti et al. (2015), little is known about the evo- lution of the
125 Pyrenean glaciers since the end of the LIA, considered in general, as the main
126 glacial advance in the Pyrenees since the beginning of the Holocene (Oliva
127 et al., 2018, 2019). The main part of the glaciated area of the Pyrenees is
128 distributed in three massifs: Maladeta-Aneto, Gavarnie-Monte Perdido, and
129 Vignemale. In a regional study involving the whole Pyrenean Range, Serrat
130 and Ventura (1993) analyzed the distribution and fluctuations of the glaciers,
131 whereas Rico et al. (2017) updated the data related to the area retreat of the
132 Pyrenean glaciers for the period 1850–2016. Later on, the “Evaluación de
133 los recursos hídricos procedentes de la innivación” (ERHIN) program
134 (ERHIN, 2007) studied the state of the Pyrenean Spanish glaciers. Most
135 research is concentrated in the Monte Perdido, Maladeta, and Vignemale
136 massifs, where the larger glaciers of the Pyrenees are located (i.e. Chueca
137 and Julian, 1996, 2004a; Chueca et al., 2003, 2005, 2009; Del Rio et al.,
138 2014; ERHIN, 2006, 2008; González-Trueba et al., 2008; López-Moreno et
139 al., 2006, 2015, 2016, 2018; Marti et al., 2015; among others).

140 Despite these studies, there is still a need to know more in detail the evolution
141 of the Pyrenean glaciers since the LIA, and especially the evolution of its
142 volume. These glaciers are among the most meridional glaciers in Europe
143 (Grunewald and Scheithauer, 2010). Due to their small size, low altitude, and
144 southern location, these glaciers are currently being recognized as highly
145 sensitive geo-indicators of climatic variations (Del Rio et al., 2014;
146 Grunewald and Scheithauer, 2010; Serrano et al., 2010, 2011). Thus, we
147 present a detailed extent, volumetric reconstruction and ice distribution
148 model of the Aneto Glacier (located in the Maladeta Massif, Central
149 Pyrenees). We focused the research in this glacier because it is the largest
150 glacier of the Pyrenees and the Pyrenean glacial remnants are useful and
151 reliable proxy indicators to analyze the impact of the current climatic
152 changes on mid-latitude mountains (Chueca et al., 2005). Accord- ing to
153 López-Moreno et al. (2016), providing evidence of past and recent changes
154 in ice volume allows to understand the evolution of the glacier in previous
155 and present periods of climate change. Moreover, the disappearance of the
156 Aneto Glacier will have negative effects on cultural ecosystem services such
157 as landscape esthetics or historical value (Grima and Campos, 2020) and eco-
158 nomic losses related to tourism. We reconstructed the glacier vol- ume for
159 seven glacial stages (LIA, 1957, 1983, 2000, 2006, 2015, 2017). We also
160 estimated the ELA of each stage and performed a paleotemperature
161 reconstruction during the LIA using an estimation of the ELA depression.

162 Study area

163 The Aneto Glacier (Figure 1) is located in the Ésera Valley, in the Maladeta
164 Massif, close to the Aneto Peak ($42^{\circ} 37' 52$ N, $0^{\circ} 39' 24$ E; 3404 m a.s.l.),
165 the highest point of the Pyrenees. The glacier is northward facing and it is
166 located on the Aneto Cirque. This glacier is surrounded by steep slopes
167 (Chueca and Julián, 2004a), and the slope of the glacier is steeper ($>30\%$) in
168 the headwall area (Figures 2a and c). Nevertheless, the middle part of the
169 glacier is also fairly steep (Figure 2b). The summits of the Maladeta Massif
170 have a preferential NW-SE orientation, from the Alba Peak to the Russell
171 Peak, and it displays morphological asymmetries (García- Ruiz et al., 1992;
172 González-García et al., 2011; Martínez de Pisón, 1986, 1989). This massif is
173 composed mainly by paleozoic granitic rocks, that belong to the Maladeta
174 batholith, characterized by a high resistance to erosive processes. The

175 morphostructural disposition of the massif (NW-SE) has determined the
176 favorable orientation of its northeast glaciers (Chueca and Lampre, 1994).

177 The climate of the Maladeta Massif is considered to be Medi- terranean. The
178 weather station at Llanos del Hospital (43°08'38" N, 6°11'00" E; 1758m
179 a.s.l.), located ~6km to the NW of the Aneto Glacier, recorded in 2019 a
180 mean annual temperature of 6.8°C, and 1057.5mm of annual precipitation
181 (according to cli- maynievepirineos.com). Close to the Aneto Glacier, the
182 Aneto weather station installed in the Maladeta Massif at 3040 m a.s.l.,
183 reported in 2018 a mean annual temperature of -1.38°C, being the minimum
184 annual temperature (-20.4°C) in February and the maximum annual
185 temperature (14.7°C) in August (Gobierno de Aragón, 2019). According to
186 López-Moreno et al., (2015), the air temperature in the Pyrenees has
187 increased at least 0.9°C since the end of the LIA (Dessens and Bücher, 1995;
188 Feuillet and Mercier, 2012), showing an increase of 0.2°C per decade
189 between 1951 and 2010 (Deaux et al., 2014). This warming trend has been
190 associated with the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), affecting the snow
191 accumulation in the Pyrenees during the second half of the 20th century, in
192 particular at high elevations (López-Moreno et al., 2007, 2011; Marti et al.,
193 2015).

194 Since the LIA, the glaciers of the Maladeta Massif have begun a retreat phase
195 until present, even though they underwent more stable periods and also less
196 significant advances (González- Trueba et al., 2008). In the Maladeta
197 Glacier, near to the Aneto Glacier, Chueca et al. (2005) pointed out that since
198 the LIA the rate of ice retreat has experienced stadials of glacial stabilization
199 (1820–1830 to 1857; 1914–1920 to 1934–1935; 1957 to 1981), moderated
200 glacial depletion (1901–1904 to 1914–1920; 1934– 1935 to 1957) and
201 marked glacial depletion (1857 to 1901–1904; 1981 to 2000). Due to the
202 proximity, it can be assumed that these stages have also taken place in the
203 Aneto Glacier.

204

205 Methods

206 Glacier extent reconstruction

207 The glacier extent during the LIA was reconstructed using the well-preserved
208 moraines. According to González-Trueba et al. (2008), in the Aneto Glacier,
209 a moraine complex made up of multiple moraine arches allows for the

210 assessment of the evolution of the glacier and indicate their stabilization
211 during the LIA (Figure 3). The mapping of the LIA moraines from the Aneto
212 Glacier was carried out based on correlations with the LIA moraines dated
213 in the Maladeta Glacier (Chueca and Julián, 1996; Chueca et al., 2005)
214 regarding the topographic level, the geomorphological similarities and their
215 spatial distribution. The location of the moraines was determined and
216 confirmed during several field work campaigns in 2017 and 2018, and
217 delimited manually using satellite images with the GIS software ESRI
218 ArcMap (version 10.5).

219 For the recent stages (1957, 1983, 2000, 2006, 2015, 2017), the glacier extent
220 was reconstructed by digitizing over satellite and aerial images. All the
221 images were provided by the “Plan Nacional de Ortofotografía Aérea”
222 (PNOA) of the “Instituto Geográfico Nacional” (IGN), except the image
223 from 2017, which was provided by the Sentinel-2 program of the European
224 Space Agency (ESA). The extension for the 1983 stage should be con-
225 sidered with caution. Due to the lower quality of the 1983 aerial image
226 (especially in the southeast part of the glacier), we supported the glacier
227 outline delimitation on that from Arenillas- Parra et al. (2008), who carried
228 out a delimitation based on aerial flights from the “Instituto Español de
229 Glaciología” (INEGLA), with flight scales between 1:25,000 and 1: 10,000.
230 Besides, due to the lower resolution of the image from 2017, in some parts
231 of the glacier the limits were verified and adjusted using Garmin GPS data
232 from a fieldwork campaign in the summer of 2017.

233 Reconstruction of the glacier digital elevation model

234 The method proposed by Schilling and Hollin (1981), based on the
235 assumption of a perfect plasticity of the glaciers, is useful for its application
236 in valleys without ice, because the geomorphological features such as
237 moraines, thresholds, trimlines, and others are necessary for the calculations.
238 In our case, there is a glacier. Thus, to apply the method properly, we
239 “removed” the actual glacier by subtracting a Digital Elevation Model
240 (DEM) of the glacier obtained by the ERHIN program (ERHIN, 2008). The
241 ERHIN program estimated the distribution of the ice thickness of the Aneto
242 and Maladeta glaciers using Geo-radar techniques, and obtained a maximum
243 ice thickness of 30 m for the Aneto Glacier in 2008. Then, the “ice thickness
244 contour lines” (ERHIN, 2008) of the glacier were digitized and a DEM was
245 created from those contours. To calibrate the ice thickness of the 2010 stage,

246 we assumed the ice thickness decreased $\sim 0.75\text{m year}^{-1}$ between 2008 and
247 2010, according to the data reported by the World Glacier Monitoring
248 Service (WGMS, 2012), which analyzed the period 2005– 2010 in Maladeta
249 Glacier, located nearby the Aneto Glacier. Thus, we created a detailed DEM
250 of the Aneto Glacier in 2010 by using the ice thickness contour lines derived
251 from ERHIN (2008). This DEM of the glacier was subtracted from a DEM
252 derived from LIDAR data from 2010 (obtained from the IGN), obtaining the
253 topography of the area without the glacier. The reconstruction of each stage
254 was calculated using this topography.

255 Numerical model

256 The combination of physically-based models supported by geo-
257 morphological evidence has been shown to be a successful method for
258 reconstructing paleoglacier topography (Campos et al., 2019; Carrasco et al.,
259 2013; Pedraza et al., 2013; Rea and Evans, 2007; Vieira, 2008). In this study
260 we used a method developed by Schilling and Hollin (1981) that adapts
261 Nye's (1952) equation of mechanical equilibrium to valley glaciers,
262 introducing a shape factor that represents the proportion of the driving stress
263 induced on the bed surface. This method, described in detail and automatized
264 by Benn and Hulton (2010), calculates the sur- face profiles of former
265 glaciers using an exact solution of a "perfectly plastic" glacier model. With
266 these ice surface profiles, a DEM is created in order to obtain the ice
267 thickness of the glacier.

268 The equation (1) proposed by Schilling and Hollin (1981), based on the
269 equation of mechanical equilibrium for an infinitely wide glacier (Nye,
270 1952), provides only a partial solution to the problem.

$$271 \quad h_{i+1} = h_i + (\tau Y / H)_i (\Delta x / \rho g) \quad (1)$$

272 Where h is the ice surface elevation, H the glacier thickness ($H = h - B$), where
273 B is the bed elevation, τY is the yield stress, Δx is a specified distance interval
274 along the x -axis, ρ is the glacier ice density ($\sim 900\text{kgm}^{-3}$) and g is the
275 gravitational acceleration (9.81m s^{-2}). To find the surface profile for an
276 irregular bed, is necessary to calculate it in a succession of discrete steps (i ,
277 $i + 1$, $i + 2$, etc) (Benn and Hulton, 2010).

278 In the equation (1), τY and H are those at step i , and unrepresentative of the
279 interval between step i and $i+1$. According to Benn and Hulton (2010),

280 because the values τ_Y and H in equation (1) are those at step i , and may be
281 unrepresentative of the interval between step i and $i+1$, there may be a
282 tendency for the calculated points to either overshoot or undershoot the
283 desired value. This problem was solved by Van der Veen (1999) in equation
284 (2), calculating the basal shear stress and ice thickness for the mid- point of
285 the interval i to $i+1$ and extracting h_{i+1} , using a quadratic equation solved by
286 factoring, setting the equation equal to zero and factor.

$$287 \quad h_{i+1}^2 - h_i + 1(B_i + B_{i+1}) \\ 288 \quad + h_i(B_{i+1} - B_i) - 2 \Delta x \tau_Y / \rho g = 0. \quad (2)$$

289

290 Finally, according to Nye's (1952) proposal, we incorporated to the equation
291 (2) (replacing τ_Y with τ_Y/f) the use of a shape factor (f), defined in equation
292 (3), to represent the proportion of the driving stress supported by the bed.

$$293 \quad f = A / Hp \quad (3)$$

294 Being A the area of the glacier cross section and p the glacierized perimeter
295 of the cross-section (Paterson, 1994). A starting value of 100kPa for the
296 entire glacier was used in this study based on Nye (1952) and Kanasevitch
297 (1963), changing it in the model along the profile where there is
298 morphological evidence of changes in ice thickness, such as moraines.

299 ELAs calculation

300 To determine the ELA of each glacier stage, we tested several methods
301 aiming to select the most appropriate. First, we applied the Area Altitude
302 Balance Ratio (AABR) proposed by Osmaston (2005), which considers the
303 hypsometry of the glacier and assumes that the mass balance gradient
304 consists of approximately two linear segments, usually with different slopes
305 above and below the ELA, and uses a balance ratio (BR) for the estimation
306 (Osmaston, 2005). The BR is the ratio of the slopes of the mass
307 balance/altitude graph below and above the ELA. According to Rea (2009),
308 the global AABR has been derived as 1.75. Despite this global ratio, we
309 chose a ratio of 1.6, that results a most appropriate value for glaciers from
310 the Central Pyrenees, which have affinities and similar regime to glaciers in
311 the Alps, where Rea (2009) calculated an AABR of 1.59 ± 0.6 .

312 The second method is the Accumulation Area Ratio (AAR), which proposes
313 a relationship between the accumulation and the ablation areas. Benn and
314 Evans (1998) pointed out that the AAR in steady-state glaciers at mid and
315 high latitudes ranges from 0.5 to 0.8. To characterize steady-state conditions
316 for valley/cirque glaciers, an AAR of 0.6 ± 0.05 is generally considered
317 (Andrews 1975; Ballantyne 1989; Gross et al. 1977; Hawkins 1985; Leon-
318 ard 1989; Locke 1989; Meierding 1982; Meier and Post 1962; Nesje 1992;
319 Porter 1975; Sutherland 1984, among others). Finally, we also used the AA
320 method, based on the assumption that the BR is 1, and therefore it is straight-
321 forward to calculate (Osmaston, 2005). The AA method is equal to the AABR
322 for a BR of 1.

323 Climatic reconstruction from LIA

324 We reconstructed the temperature during the LIA multiplying the ELA
325 depression (Δ ELA) by a modern lapse rate. Although ELAs of glaciers which
326 are not in equilibrium with climate may not accurately reflect the
327 temperature, the Maladeta Glacier represents a fine example to test the
328 relationship between climate and glacier fluctuations (Chueca et al., 2005).
329 We assume that the relationship in the Aneto Glacier (located right next to
330 Maladeta Glacier) is similar. The Δ ELA was obtained using the ELA from
331 LIA and the modern ELA (2017), whereas a modern lapse rate of
332 $0.517^{\circ}\text{C}/100\text{m}$ proposed for the Pyrenees Range by Navarro-Serrano et al.
333 (2017, 2018) was applied. This lapse rate was chosen because it is more
334 accurate (local estimation) compared to the most widely used mean
335 environmental lapse rate (a linear decrease of $0.65^{\circ}\text{C}/100\text{ m}$).

336 Uncertainties

337 There are several uncertainties associated with the applied methods. For the
338 glacier outlines delimitation, the uncertainty varies depending on the quality
339 of the image used for the delimitation. Aerial images of 1957, 1983, 2000,
340 2006, and 2015 provided by the IGN have a cell size resolution between 0.5
341 and 0.95m per pixel, whereas the image from Sentinel-2 used for the
342 delimitation of the glacier area in 2017 was provided by ESA and has a
343 resolution of 10 m per pixel. To address and minimize the effects of this
344 uncertainty, we supported our delimitation with data obtained during a field
345 work campaign in summer 2017 that confirms the glacier extent. According
346 to Williams et al. (1997) when using satellite images, “local knowledge” of

347 glaciers is critically important in the accurate delineation of glacier margins.
348 Furthermore, the results provided are in line with field observations.

349 Regarding the glacier DEM calculation process, some uncertainties could be
350 produced when digitizing the contour lines of the ice thicknesses obtained
351 by ERHIN program (ERHIN, 2008). These uncertainties depend on the skills
352 and precision of the scientist when digitizing. Although these digitized
353 contour lines should be considered with caution, we performed each step as
354 accurately as possible, obtaining consistent results. There are also some
355 uncertainties related to the reconstruction method itself, in which they are
356 not taken into account the effects of longitudinal stresses and their gradients.
357 However, these effects appear to be small (Weertman, 1961) and not seemed
358 important for the calculation of the ice volumes (Schilling and Hollin, 1981).

359 Results

360 The results of the reconstruction and analysis of the glacial stages from the
361 LIA, 1957, 1983, 2000, 2006, 2015, and 2017 show the volume evolution
362 and the ice distribution of the Aneto Glacier and the variations of the surface
363 and temperatures.

364 Morphometric parameters

365 From the LIA to 2017, the length of the Aneto Glacier decreased from 1970
366 to 675m (~66% of its initial length). The glacier front descended to 2385 m
367 a.s.l. during the LIA, while in 2017 the glacier front lay at 3029 m a.s.l.
368 (Table 1). Regarding the width of the head of the glacier, from LIA to 1957
369 its northwestern part has been reduced by 120 m. From 1957 to 2015 there
370 were barely any variations in the width of the header. For the last 2 years of
371 the analysis, from 2015 to 2017, the southeast part has disconnected from the
372 “main glacier,” losing 15–20m of ice (Table 1 and Figure 4). Finally, the
373 glacier area has been drastically reduced from 245 ha in the LIA to 48.64ha
374 in 2017. This process has accelerated since 1957, having lost in 2017 ~58%
375 of the area estimated for 1957.

376 Basal topography estimation

377 The computed basal topography of the area allowed for the reconstruction of
378 the volume of the glacier and its ice thickness in all the studied stages (Figure
379 5). The calculation also shows the basal topography and the slope of the
380 glacier. Thus, the basal topography occupied by the glacier during the LIA

381 has its steepest slope on the lower part (Figure 6a), with a maximum
382 inclination of 67% and a mean inclination of ~25%. Furthermore, we observe
383 that the mean and maximum slopes of the basal topography decrease as the
384 glacier retreats, indicating that the upper part has less inclination. However,
385 during all the stages, one of the steepest slopes is logically located in the part
386 of the cirque walls (Figure 6b).

387 Volume and ice thickness distribution

388 The ice thickness reconstruction of the Aneto glacier and its distribution
389 during the LIA, 1957, 1983, 2000, 2006, 2015, and 2017 is presented in
390 Figure 7. During the LIA, the glacier had a volume of ice of $82.57 \text{ m} \times 10^6$
391 m^3 . This volume was reduced to $32.87 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ in 1957, approximately
392 60%, and to $22.29 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ in 1983 (~73%). In 2000, the volume was
393 $11.68 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$, and continued decreasing up to $3.48 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ in 2017
394 (Table 2). That means a total reduction of ~96% of the volume of the glacier
395 in the period LIA–2017. The maximum ice thickness also decreased from 95
396 m in LIA to 27 m in 2017 (Figure 7a–g), a 62%, being a large part of this
397 reduction in the period 1957–2017.

398 Despite the thinning of the glacier, the distribution of the ice has been similar
399 throughout the studied period, being the upper areas and the western part
400 those with more thickness in the period 2000–2017. During the LIA, there
401 were also areas with large ice thickness in the parts corresponding to the flow
402 lines of both tongues (Figure 7a).

403 ELAs of the Aneto Glacier

404 The ELA values for each stage were calculated using different methods and
405 are presented in Table 2. The three methods used for the ELA calculation
406 gave similar results, especially the AAR and AABR methods. We chose the
407 AABR ELA as the most accurate method because it takes into account the
408 hypsometry of the glacier. Using the AABR method (with ratio = 1.6) we
409 obtained an ELA for the LIA of 2919 m a.s.l., which reached 3081 m a.s.l. in
410 1957 and 3089 m a.s.l. in 1983. In this century, the ELA ranged from
411 3105 m a.s.l. in 2000 to 3139 m a.s.l. in 2017. These data indicate a clear
412 upward trend of the ELA at the Aneto Glacier. The trend from the 2000 stage
413 shows and acceleration in the increase of ELA (more than LIA–2000 period),
414 as well as for the reduction trend of the maximum ice thickness (Figure 8).
415 However, the special geometry of the glacier (having two lobes and being

416 the glacier wider than larger) contributed to maintain the percentage of the
417 accumulation area in relation to the total area of the glacier, practically
418 unchanged since the LIA.

419 Paleotemperatures at the end of the LIA

420 By using a modern environmental lapse rate and the Δ ELA, we obtained the
421 temperature during the LIA. The Δ ELA between the modern ELA
422 (3139ma.s.l.) and the LIA ELA (2919ma.s.l.) is 220m. Multiplying this
423 Δ ELA by the lapse rate of -0.00517 ($-0.517^{\circ}\text{C}/100\text{m}$), the result shows that
424 the temperature during the LIA was $\sim 1.14^{\circ}\text{C}$ colder than in 2017. Assuming
425 this temperature variation and the mean annual temperature of -0.61°C
426 (reported by the weather station nearby the Aneto Glacier for the year 2017),
427 we obtained a mean annual temperature of $\sim -1.75^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the LIA in the
428 Aneto Glacier.

429

430 Discussion

431 Moraine record of LIA

432 The extent of the glacier during the LIA was determined by using several
433 moraines, which are characterized by a well-preserved morphology. The
434 moraines are located from ~ 2385 m a.s.l. (frontal moraines) to 2800–3050
435 m a.s.l. (lateral moraines), coinciding with those reported by Chueca and
436 Julian (1996, 2004a), referring to the LIA. González-Trueba et al. (2008)
437 suggested that LIA moraines are located at 2350 m a.s.l. as the lowest altitude
438 in the Aneto Glacier, almost the same altitude we reported in our research.
439 Near the Aneto Glacier, in the Maladeta Glacier, Chueca et al. (2005) used
440 as LIA moraines those dated around 1820–1830 by Chueca and Julián (1996)
441 from morainic deposits. After that, between 1820 and 1830 and 1857, the
442 glacier was stabilized and its morphology remained almost unchanged
443 (Chueca et al., 2005). Furthermore, González-Trueba et al. (2008), pointed
444 out that a retreat phase began after 1820, which has been constant until
445 present day, although it underwent more stable periods and also less
446 significant advances. All this indicates that the LIA moraines remained
447 unchanged and have not been affected by other important advances. These
448 moraines dated by Chueca and Julian (1996) have similar dimensions,
449 morphologies, and continuity than those we used to delimitate the area of the
450 Aneto Glacier during the LIA. Also, in the Maladeta Glacier, the LIA

451 moraines descend to the same altitude that in Aneto Glacier (González-
452 Trueba et al., 2008). Therefore, all these studies confirm that the moraines
453 chosen to delimitate the LIA extent of the Aneto Glacier are appropriate and
454 certainly belong to that glacial stage.

455 Glacier reconstruction

456 The glacier reconstruction for the LIA, 1957, 1983, 2000, 2006, 2015, and
457 2017 show the area, ice thickness distribution, and volume of the Aneto
458 Glacier. The area obtained for the LIA stage was 245 ha, which coincide with
459 the data from González-Trueba et al. (2008), who reported 236 ha. Martínez
460 de Pisón (1989), based on data collected by Franz Schrader in 1876, reported
461 228 ha, also a similar result than our study. For the 1957 stage, we obtained
462 an area of ~115ha, the same area reported by ERHIN (2006).

463 There is no more data from other authors for this stage, which could be a
464 consequence of the difficulty of the glacier delimitation based on the quality
465 of the base image. For the 1983 stage, we reported an extent of ~103ha, that
466 is slightly different from the 136 ha obtained by Arenillas-Parra et al. (2008)
467 for 1982, However, it coincides with the ~107 ha reported by ERHIN
468 (2006) for 1983, who calculated the area based in INEGLA's flight. Further-
469 more, the area of the following stages (2000, 2006, 2015, and 2017) are in
470 line with data reported in previous research (ERHIN, 2007, 2008; Rico et al.,
471 2017) for similar periods. Regarding the glaciated area change, our results
472 show a drastic decrease corresponding to 80% of the glaciated area from the
473 LIA to 2017. Other reconstructions performed in Pyrenean glaciers, for
474 similar time frames, such as Maladeta Glacier (Chueca et al., 2003; 2005)
475 and Monte Perdido Glacier (López-Moreno et al., 2015, 2016, 2018) suggest
476 a similar shrinkage since LIA, which accelerated during the last decades.
477 However, data related to the Ossoue Glacier (Marti et al., 2015) shows that
478 the retreat rate is less pronounced (60%; LIA–2013) than in the Aneto (this
479 study: 78%; LIA–2015), probably due to the local topography and the
480 climatic conditions of the Ossoue Glacier, which contains two-thirds of the
481 overall area in the plateau (Marti et al., 2015) and is under the influence of
482 the North Atlantic westerlies that provide abundant precipitation (Chueca et
483 al., 2008). Thus, all these results indicate a clear decreasing trend of the area
484 of the Aneto Glacier since the LIA, similar trend than recorded in Maladeta
485 and Monte Perdido glaciers.

486 The calculations in the Aneto Glacier also show how the glacier volume has
487 reduced by 96% since the LIA to 2017 (from 82.57 to 3.48m \times 106m³), and
488 the maximum ice thickness has reduced from 95 to 27 m during the same
489 period. Although there are no similar reconstructions that encompass that
490 period in the Aneto Glacier, we observe that the results we obtained for the
491 year 2006 (37 m of ice thickness and 8.25 m \times 106 m³ of volume) are similar
492 to the data provided by the ERHIN program (30 m of ice thickness and
493 7.62m \times 106m³ of volume in the year 2008; ERHIN, 2008), confirming the
494 validity of our methods. In the Pyrenees, only a few estimates of ice volume
495 loss have been published (Lopez-Moreno et al., 2016), such as in the
496 Maladeta Glacier, where Chueca et al. (2005) obtained a reduction of the
497 glacier volume of 13.7m \times 106m³ for the period 1981–2005. These results are
498 in accordance to those reported in the present study of 14.04 m \times 106 m³
499 from 1983 to 2006 in the Aneto Glacier considering the corresponding time
500 frame. Moreover, Marti et al. (2015) obtained a volume decrease of 21.9 m
501 \times 106 m³ in the Ossoue Glacier during the period 1983–2013. This value is
502 a similar result to the 17.6m \times 106m³ obtained in the present study for the
503 period 1983–2015 (considering both time frames). Therefore, all these
504 studies pointed out a consistent trend of area and volume loss of the studied
505 Pyrenean glaciers.

506 ELAs of the Aneto Glacier

507 Three methods were applied in this study to calculate the ELA of the Aneto
508 Glacier in all the stages: the AA, AAR, and AABR. The most reliable results
509 were obtained with the AABR method, since it considers the hypsometry of
510 the glacier, avoiding possible errors associated to the hypsometric effect,
511 which occurs when the AAR method is used. Thus, we obtained an ELA of
512 2919 m a.s.l. during the LIA (AABR, ratio 1.6) that agrees with previous
513 estimations for the Aneto Glacier (2909 m a.s.l, González-Trueba et al.,
514 2008),

515 for the Maladeta Glacier (2840 m a.s.l., Chueca and Julián, 2004b; 2905 m
516 a.s.l., González-Trueba et al., 2008) and the Ésera Water- shed (snowline
517 altitude of 2900 m a.s.l., Julián and Chueca, 1998). These homogeneous ELA
518 values implies a clear widespread of these glaciers of the Central Pyrenees
519 during the LIA associated with colder conditions than in the modern climate.

520 For 1957, 1983, and 2000, we estimated an ELA of 3081, 3089, and 3105 m
521 a.s.l., respectively. These results are similar to the data reported in the
522 Maladeta Glacier by Chueca and Julián (2004b) and Chueca et al. (2005),
523 who suggested ELAs of 3030, 3035, and 3095m a.s.l. for the years 1957,
524 1981, and 1997–99, respectively. The small difference between our ELAs of
525 1957 and 1983 in the Aneto Glacier and the ELA determined by Chueca and
526 Julián (2004b) in Maladeta Glacier could be due to the different topography
527 of the glaciers, which can cause notable variations in the ELAs of different
528 glaciers in the same region (Carrivick and Brewer, 2004; López-Moreno et
529 al., 2006, 2016; Reinwarth and Escher-Vetter, 1999). A similar difference is
530 observed between our ELA of 2015 located at 3134 m a.s.l., and the value of
531 3050 m a.s.l. for the period 2011–2014 obtained by López-Moreno et al.,
532 (2016, 2018) in Monte Perdido Glacier (Gavarnie-Monte Perdido Massif),
533 which is related to the location and the local topography of the glacier.
534 Therefore, it is necessary to consider local topography in future ELA
535 reconstructions, being the AABR the most appropriated method for these
536 reconstructions.

537 Paleotemperatures during the LIA

538 Our results show a mean annual temperature of -1.75°C in the Aneto Glacier
539 during the LIA, a temperature $\sim 1.14^{\circ}\text{C}$ lower in relation to 2017 (-0.61°C).
540 For a timeframe from the LIA to 2000, we obtained a temperature lapse of
541 $\sim 0.96^{\circ}\text{C}$. This temperature decrease coincides with the estimations proposed
542 by Julián and Chueca (1998), who suggested that the temperatures during the
543 LIA were $0.90/0.95^{\circ}\text{C}$ lower than those at the end of the 90's in the southern
544 Central Pyrenees and González-Trueba et al. (2008) that reported an increase
545 of temperature of around 0.9°C in the Iberian high mountains since the LIA.
546 However, our temperature decrease estimation does not match with the
547 values suggested by Serrano (1996, 1998) and Lampre (1994, 1998), who
548 suggested tempera- ture fluctuations and variations of 0.76°C and 0.71°C
549 since the LIA to the 90's in Infierno-Panticosa and Maladeta massifs,
550 respectively. The small differences between Serrano (1996, 1998) and
551 Lampre (1994, 1998) and our results could be associated with the
552 temperature calculation using a Mean ELA (MELA) of several glaciers
553 within a whole massif, while we used only the local ELA calculated for the
554 Aneto Glacier. This underscores the importance of the topographical features

555 and the asymmetry between northern and southern faces in relation to the
556 ELAs, and consequentially to the temperature calculation.

557 Implications of the retreat and disappearance of the Aneto Glacier

558 A continuous retreat or disappearance of the Aneto Glacier will not only have
559 consequences related to local ecosystems (due to the glacier being a natural
560 water reservoir), but also economic consequences related to the regional
561 tourism industry. The land- scape will change, and as a consequence, the
562 number of visitors associated with glacier and mountain activities may
563 decrease, which in turn will affect the economy of local communities. Fur-
564 thermore, the disappearance of the Aneto Glacier will mean the loss of one
565 of the southernmost glaciers as a climatic proxy.

566 Our data show a loss of the ice volume of $\sim 0.46 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$ between the
567 LIA and 1957. This rate decreased to $\sim 0.41 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$ in the 1957–
568 1983 period and increased again to $\sim 0.6 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$ in the 1983–
569 2000 period, coinciding with a stadial of glacial depletion in Maladeta
570 Glacier pointed out by Chueca et al. (2005). Hereafter, the rate was $\sim 0.57 \times$
571 $10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$ in the 2000–2006 period. Finally, the volume loss rate
572 decreased in the period 2006–2015 ($\sim 0.4 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$) and increased again
573 in the period 2015–2017 ($\sim 0.6 \text{ m} \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$). The deceleration of the
574 ratio in the period 2006–2015 could be due to the increase of the ice thickness
575 in the year 2010 in the Maladeta Glacier, located nearby the Aneto Glacier,
576 and for which we assume a similar behavior. The Maladeta Glacier increased
577 259 of specific annual balance in mm water equivalent (mm w.e.) (WGMS,
578 2012) in the balance year 2009/2010, equivalent to $\sim 28 \text{ cm}$ of thickness.
579 These data not change the recent trend because in 2011 the thickness
580 decreased again. According to WGMS (2013), the Maladeta Glacier
581 decreased in 1504 mm w.e. in the balance year 2010/2011, equivalent to
582 $\sim 1.67 \text{ m}$ of thickness. The data related to the glacier extent of the Aneto
583 Glacier show a similar trend. From the LIA to 2000, the rate of loss of
584 glaciated area was $1.08 \text{ ha}/\text{year}$, while the rate in the 2000–2017 period was
585 $2.03 \text{ ha}/\text{year}$. If the current trend continues, the Aneto Glacier could disappear
586 or be reduced to a remnant of ice by the middle of this century or the
587 following decades.

588 Conclusions

589 We present a reconstruction of the Aneto Glacier since the LIA during several
590 glacial stages (LIA, 1957, 1983, 2000, 2006, 2015, and 2017). The
591 reconstruction was performed by using numerical models, which proved to
592 be useful for the reconstruction of former glacial stages. The results show a
593 reduction of the glacier area from 245 to 48.64ha for the LIA–2017period.
594 For the same period, the glacier volume has reduced from 82.57 to 3.48 m ×
595 106 m³, and the maximum ice thickness decreased from 95 m during the LIA
596 to 27 m in 2017. The results also show ELAs ranging from 2919 to 3139 m
597 a.s.l. and a temperature increase of ~1.14°C from the LIA to 2017. These
598 results indicate a drastic retreat of the glacier since the LIA, and also an
599 acceleration of the wastage since 1983 and even more since the year 2000.
600 This study provides robust data indicating that if this trend continues, by the
601 middle or second half of the century the Aneto Glacier will have disappeared
602 or it will have become an ice patch.

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Figure 1. Location map of the study area with outlined glaciated area in 2006

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Figure 2. (a) View of the Aneto Glacier from the NW. (b) Slope of the middle-upper part of the Aneto Glacier and its steep headwall. (c) Partial view of the Maladeta Massif from near the Aneto Peak, the Aneto Glacier is located on the right slope, facing north. (Photo credit: Néstor Campos and Jesús Alcalá, 2018).

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954
 955 Figure 3. LIA moraines of the Aneto Glacier, based on chronological data
 956 from González-Trueba et al. (2008). (a) Black dashed lines indicating the
 957 moraines over a Google Earth image. (b) Yellow dashed lines showing lateral
 958 moraines over a picture taken from the west part of the mountain (Photo
 959 credit: Néstor Campos and Jesús Alcalá, 2018).

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961
 962 Figure 4. Glacier extent reconstruction for the studied glacial stages. The LIA
 963 reconstruction was based on moraines and the other glacial stages were
 964 reconstructed by using satellite and aerial images.

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 967 Figure 5. Basal topography of the glacier. Top image: ice thickness derived
 968 from ERHIN (2008). Left image: DEM of the area. Right image: DEM of
 969 the area “without” the glacier.

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 972 Figure 6. Slope map (%) of the basal topography of the glacier area in (a)
 973 LIA and (b) 2017.

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 976 Figure 7. Ice thickness distribution of the Aneto glacier. (a) LIA, (b) 1957,
 977 (c) 1983, (d) 2000, (e) 2006, (f) 2015, (g) 2017.

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 980 Figure 8. ELAs and Maximum Ice Thickness for the studied periods. Green
 981 dashed lines indicate the trend from 2000 to 2017 and black lines indicated
 982 the trend from LIA to 2000.

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984 Table 1. Evolution of the morphometric parameters of the glacier.

	Length (m)	Altitude (m)		Header width (m)	Area (ha)	Slope (°)	
		Maximum	Minimum			Mean	Maximum
LIA	1970	3271	2385	1900	245	24.91	67
1957	1050	3284	2748	1780	114.77	24.06	60
1983	921	3314	2828	1778	103.2	24.01	59
2000	830	3308	2929	1775	83.2	23.97	57
2006	730	3275	2935	1770	69.27	23.46	56
2015	690	3270	2985	1770	52.54	23.43	56
2017	675	3269	3029	1480 + 200*	48.64	23.6	56

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*The southeast part of the glacier head has disconnected from the "main glacier." Thus, the header has divided in two separate ice masses.

986

987 Table 2. Volumes, maximum ice thicknesses, and ELAs corresponding to the
988 studied periods.

	Volume ($\times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$)	Max Ice Thickness (m)	ELA AA	ELA AAR	ELA AABR	
				Ratio 0.6	Ratio 1.6	Ratio 1.75
LIA	82.57	95	2958	2922	2919	2911
1957	32.87	80	3099	3083	3081	3077
1983	22.29	55	3105	3093	3089	3086
2000	11.68	45	3118	3113	3105	3102
2006	8.25	37	3125	3120	3113	3110
2015	4.69	29	3143	3137	3134	3132
2017	3.48	27	3147	3140	3139	3137

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